

PRIME PETE

PRIMARY EDUCATION PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER EDUCATION

Recommendations on Primary Physical Education Teacher Education

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Technical sheet

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Recommendations on Primary Physical Education Teacher Education

Project partners:

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Introduction

This document reports the work done during the Primary Education Physical Education Teacher Education (PRIME PETE) project development in order to formulate the *Recommendations on Primary Physical Education Teacher Education* intending to provide a basis and rationale for the development and implementation of future primary Physical Education Teacher Education (PETE) programmes.

After a landscape analysis of PETE in Europe took place during intellectual output (IO) 1, the recommendations build on a literature review that aimed to identify and highlight findings from the published literature that can inform the development of the PRIME PETE programme. Secondly, a Delphi study was conducted to find a consensus among experts on which aspects of primary PETE are most important. Furthermore, the recommendations will be derived from a mapping of and an exchange on the primary PETE course modules the Higher Education Institutions (HEI) project partners are offering in the existing programmes at their institutions. At the beginning all HEI partner institutions that are active in primary PETE and implement respective study programmes in their respective national contexts, shared and learned from each other how the respective primary PETE programmes look like and what experiences partners were able to make during the past years when implementing those programmes. This kind of mapping and exchange amongst partners, together with the analysis during IO1 was necessary to formulate valid recommendations on Primary PETE.

Besides the project partners, who will need and use the recommendations as a basis for the projects' further development the target groups addressed were the following: Teacher education institutions; Teacher educators; Researchers active in the field of teacher education; Primary teachers teaching primary physical education (PE); NGOs like research associations, teacher associations, etc.; Stakeholders and policy makers in charge of teacher education.

The recommendations made below result from an integration work of the recommendations arising from three sources of the project: the output of the literature review and the output of the Delphi study - resulting from IO1 – and the Learning, and the Teaching or Training Activities (LTT) 1 output during the project. The analysis and integration between information output obtained from the LTT and Delphi study output was easy and established in a concrete format. As for the integration of the suggestions arising from the literature review, the recommendations

were formulated in a more generic way, allowing some of them to be considered in more than one of the dimensions formulated through the Delphi study.

In the following, the recommendations are allocated to the dimensions formulated through the Delphi study. The sources of the recommendations are indicated in each case. The recommendations could be based on one, two or three of the considered sources.

Dimension 1 - Knowledge, Development and Management

Recommendation #1

Delphi Study – Rank top 3

- Advanced knowledge and understanding of the development of fundamental movement skills
- Knowledge about children’s overall development
- Knowledge of physical activity recommendations for children and young people

Literature Review

- An increase in PE ECTS-load within the degrees preparing prospective PE teachers is necessary.

LTT

- Minimum compulsory ECTS for specific PE subjects (by increase the existing or including modules or teaching units), for both generalist and specialist teacher education.

Recommendation #2

Delphi Study – Rank top 3 (as former recommendation)

Literature Review

- Future generalist teachers should consider the child’s natural disposition towards movement and perspectives of their cognitive development through movement, such as maintaining a certain level of well-being and health.
- An increase in PE ECTS-load within the degrees preparing prospective PE teachers is necessary.
- Primary PE teachers should develop specialised knowledge, ability and competences related to PE, to be able to teach effectively.
- Advanced knowledge and understanding of the development of fundamental movement skills.

LTT

- Education courses for specialist and generalist primary school teachers must have subjects or modules that allow to analyse children's overall development and, advanced knowledge and understanding of motor development and learning of children between 5 and 10 years and its implications for the teaching-learning of PE.
- Knowledge about children's overall development

Recommendation #3

Delphi Study – Rank top 3 (as former recommendation)

Literature Review

- It is crucial to propose advocacy for PE to counteract biases towards other curriculum priorities.
- Education courses for specialists and generalist primary school teachers must have subjects or modules that able to justify the integration of PE in the multidisciplinary educational process of primary education (for instance by using multidisciplinary work groups).

Recommendation #4

Delphi Study – Rank top 3 (as former recommendation)

Literature Review

- Teacher education programmes convey a message consistent with the curriculum based on a broad and balanced curriculum and support new teachers to deliver PE within an educational ideology.
- Well-designed school experiences should be included in teacher education programmes to help participants to become familiar with the realities of teaching the curriculum and feel more empowered to teach PE in a meaningful manner.
- Teacher educators should acknowledge, address and, where necessary, challenge students' attitudes and beliefs to ensure that the key messages of their teacher education programmes translate into teacher practices.
- Primary PE teacher education should increase teachers' knowledge about the national guidelines related to the PE curriculum.

Recommendations on Primary Physical Education Teacher Education

LTT

- Education courses for specialists and generalists primary school teachers must have subjects or modules oriented towards the knowledge of the PE curriculum in primary school and its impact over later learning experiences along all the schooling time and life time.
- Knowledge of physical activity recommendations for children and young people

Recommendation #5

Delphi Study – Rank top 3 (as former recommendation)

LTT

- Knowledge that allows to develop and put into practice the official curriculum of primary education in PE

Recommendation #6

Delphi Study – Rank top 3 (as former recommendation)

LTT

- Subjects or Modules oriented to improve the teaching-learning competence focus on the pedagogical content knowledge (focused on how students are learning the PE contents, the key focus improve PE teaching in primary).

Dimension 2 – Teaching, Learning and Assessment

Recommendation #7

Delphi Study – Rank top 3

- Ability to plan and teach quality PE lessons
- Ability to provide a positive and safe learning environment
- Ability to plan long-term and short-term PE programmes based on students' developmental level and readiness

Literature Review

- Curricula enhancement is desirable, especially towards the creation of adequate learning situations and positive learning climates, as well as a towards competence- orientation in PE.
- Understanding the elements of instructional quality is an asset for future PE teachers.

Recommendations on Primary Physical Education Teacher Education

- Among particular curricula contents, a special role is addressed to digitalisation, inclusion and experiential education.
- Routines are an essential aspect related to group/classroom management.
- The design, management and processes of learning, teaching and assessment should include ungraded assessments in the area of PE teaching experience, where possible. Mentoring by PE teacher educators is crucial to this process as well as critical reflection and peer feedback from pre-service teachers.
- Self-reflection on aspects of learning from ‘practical’ modules towards the pre-service teachers’ future teaching should be an element in module assessments.
- Creating a positive attitude towards PE with future generalist teachers is a necessary base to ensure later quality implementation.
- Ability to plan and teach quality PE lessons
- Ability to provide a positive and safe learning environment
- Ability to plan long-term and short-term PE programmes based on students’ developmental level and readiness

LTT

- Subjects or modules oriented to improve the teaching-learning competence focused on pedagogical content knowledge (focused on how students are learning the PE contents, the key focus improve PE teaching in primary)
- High rate of compulsory practical classes or practical experiences in context that allow contact with the specificity of PE teaching

Dimension 3 - Learner Empowerment, Potential, Diversity, and Creativity

Recommendation #8

Delphi Study – Rank top 3

- Capacity and commitment to support the learning and development of all students regardless of their ability levels
- Capacity and commitment to motivate, inspire learners and support their empowerment
- Capacity and commitment to create situations and climates in which learners increase their self-esteem and confidence

Literature Review

- The development of a teacher's knowledge is an iterative process; anyone involved in the education of young people must be mindful that knowledge needs reviewing.
- Future teachers should reflect on their personality and dispositions, and it is recommended that future physical educators reflect on their prerequisites.
- Sports experiences at school are an opportunity for primary teachers to experience motor skills through content and activities that mobilise the psycho-affective and social areas and assist the individual growth of the teacher.
- Training courses for generalist teachers should providing adequate time to teach PE teaching methods, and promote a holistic vision of this subject that affects physical, social, health development, as well as cognitive and emotional development.
- PE teacher educators should support pre-service teachers to get positive attitudes and to develop self-efficacy beliefs towards PE.
- Acquiring psychological knowledge during studies strengthens the ability to deal with the job-related tasks of future PE teachers. Therefore, Bachelor's and Master's degree programmes should integrate targeted measures to strengthen mental health at an early stage in the first training phase and take appropriate psychological content into account in the curriculum;
- Teacher educators should support a healthy work-related behavioural and experience development.
- Professional biography support is needed in the initial teacher training phase.
- Emphasis should be placed on the health and wellbeing of PE teachers by supporting active reflection about their job.

Dimension 4 - Values and Social Leadership, and Communication

Recommendation #9

Delphi Study – Rank top 3

- Capacity and commitment to the healthy development of primary school students
- Ability to communicate effectively both verbally and non-verbally
- Ability to promote ethical behaviour in learners and foster a culture of valuing diversity within the classroom setting

Literature Review

- There is an urgent need to reinforce the workload in the PE area by changing the current curriculum matrix.
- It is imperative to reflect on sustainable PE teaching models in the organisation of school groups.
- It is necessary and fundamental to involve all teachers in the sustainability of PE for students of the first cycle of basic mandatory education (primary as well as secondary school teachers).
- There is an urgent need to profit from forms of collaborative work between specialist as generalist teachers, which contribute to the regularity and increasing quality of PE at this level of education.
- It is imperative to respect the local dynamics of each set of primary and secondary schools, in the context of the organisation's culture as a promoter of Physical Activity and Sport.
- It is essential to clarify the educational purposes of each activity (Physical Education and School Sport) and expand the benefits of its complementarity in favour of student learning.
- It is desirable to articulate with school groups/projects and local dynamics in the promotion of physical activity and sports development, in a global logic of social promotion of a Motor Culture.
- It would be useful to encourage teachers to engage with a more collaborative teaching approach that takes into account the contribution of PE **and** the PE teacher in the entire educational process.
- There is a call for a standards-based approach to beginning teacher standards to improve the status of PE both in university and school contexts and to allow accountability and quality assurance.
- In the preparation of future PE teachers, a university seminar combining didactics with practical parts is recommended; the relation between knowledge of inclusive theories and practical examples is fruitful.
- The current aims should be reflection and modification of attitudes and partly also enlarging knowledge.
- There should be a focus on the demands placed on PE teachers, learning to implement in case studies already during initial teacher education.
- Inclusive PE should be incorporated in the qualification of PE teachers.
- Friendly, supportive, and inclusive environments should be developed because they are likely to promote physical activity, especially for groups who are traditionally marginalised, such as girls or overweight children.

Recommendations on Primary Physical Education Teacher Education

- Future teachers (and other school staff) are vitally important in creating this climate, by promoting and enforcing relevant rules and norms, promoting positive peer relationships, and celebrating diversity.
- Individualisation, diversity, and special educational needs of the practical proposals that future PE teacher educators should implement in teachers' professional contexts, are highlighted as an area in which future training needs should be influenced.
- Training programmes should be provided regularly for teachers.
- As future teachers, it is essential to propose group playful motor activities in the classroom aimed at discovering values such as collaboration and trust in others and mutually help.
- Teaching must be oriented towards learning and encouraging fair play and respect for the rules and others.

Dimension 5 – Development as Reflective Professionals and Life-long Learners

Recommendation #10

Delphi Study – Rank top 3

- Capacity and commitment to actively advocate for PE in the school and beyond

Literature Review

- Teacher education should consider the importance of using effectively both ways of communication, meaning verbal and non-verbal.
- The use of the body as non-verbal communication should be encouraged in PE lessons.
- Regular professional exchanges, and lesson observation are desirable.
- Collaborations between schools and universities should be established to allow bilateral (school – university) support for PE students.
- Fruitful dialogue between future teachers and pupils is especially supportive to co-construct curricula or when it comes to inclusive PE (it allows to consider the child's view).
- Communication should be increased between teachers and parents, as well as between general teachers and specialist teachers of extracurricular physical activity.
- The use of social media and communication technologies may be beneficial for exchange between teachers acting as reflective practitioners.

Conclusions

During the production of IO2, the project team prepared the integration of the information collected from the three mentioned sources of information: Literature review, Delphi Study and the LTT 1. The above integration resulted in the formulation of five dimensions of suggestions where, in some, the contribution of these three sources of information come together, in others, only two.

In dimension 1 related to the promotion of *Knowledge, Development and Management*, which refers more specifically to knowledge about teaching and learning in PE, six recommendations are made. In dimensions 2, 3, 4 and 5 referred, respectively, to *teaching, learning and assessment; learner empowerment, potential, diversity and creativity; values, social leadership and communication and development as reflective professionals and life-long learners* only one recommendation is made per each.

These suggestions should be considered as guiding references for the design of IO3 and IO4, i.e., the *Primary Physical Education Teacher Profile* and the *Theoretical and Methodological Framework for Primary Physical Education Teacher Education* in Europe